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EFFECTS OF PROCESS CONDITIONS ON AEROSPACE GRADE EPOXY/CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

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Introduction

- Aerospace composite production demands are still increasing
- Alternative processing methods can help to increase rate
- New processing methods require comprehensive validation and qualification
- This study shows some initial promising results when curing composites using isostatic heat transfer fluid
- Initial process quality metrics used were:
 - Interlaminar Shear Strength
 - Void Content
 - Surface Porosity

Methodology

Material: Hexcel® HexPly® F584™ prepreg

Layup:[0]_{8T}, compaction after ply 1 and 4.

Experiment #	Cure process	Pressure applied	Heating rate	Dwell Temperature	Dwell Time
1	Autoclave	80 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
2	Autoclave	250 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
3	Autoclave	620 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
4	Qure	80 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	120 minutes
5	Qure	250 kPa	2°C/min	177°C	60 minutes
6	Qure	250 kPa	5°C/min	177°C	60 minutes

Interlaminar Shear Strength

Void Content

Cure process	Pressure applied	Heating rate		
Autoclave	80 kPa	2°C/min	1.06%	
	250 kPa		0.01%	
	620 kPa		0.00%	
Qure	80 kPa	2°C/min	0.31%	
	250 kPa		0.08%	
	250 kPa	5°C/min	0.00%	

Surface Porosity

Cure process	80 kPa 2°C/min	250 kPa 2°C/min	620 kPa 2°C/min
Autoclave	<p>0.00%</p>		

Cure process	80 kPa 2°C/min	250 kPa 2°C/min	250 kPa 5°C/min
Qure	<p>0.04%</p>		

Conclusions

- Interlaminar Shear Strength
 - No detrimental effect compared to autoclave when curing at lower pressure or faster heating when using isostatic processing
- Internal porosity
 - Isostatic processing at 2.5 bar resulted in similar porosity to 2.5 and 6.2 bar Autoclave specimens
 - A faster heating rate resulted in less voids
- Surface porosity
 - Isostatic processing at 2.5 bar resulted in similar porosity to 2.5 and 6.2 bar Autoclave specimens
 - A faster heating rate resulted in less surface porosity

Future work:

- Thicker laminates
- Faster heating rates
- Modelling of kinetics and rheology
- Initiate aerospace qualification testing program